

FOCUS-GROUP DISCUSSIONS LAUNCHED

AND IMPLEMENTED

DELIAH

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1 INTRODUCTION

Democratic Literacy and Humour (DELIAH) examines the multifaceted role of humour in artistic forms, cultural spaces, and both online and offline forums, exploring how humour can either support or undermine democratic participation and processes across Europe. Work Package 2 of the project involves conducting thirty focus groups — five in each of the six countries represented in the consortium — with the aim of uncovering social discourses on humour and politics, and of evaluating participants' responses to humorous stimuli. In this context, politics is understood in a broad sense — hence, the use of the expression *socio-political* humour. This encompasses any form of humorous practice or content that influences, or is deployed to influence, how people perceive and engage with democratic processes and public institutions, as well as how they perceive and relate to other social groups and prevailing social norms.

This document presents: *i*) the design of the focus groups, encompassing their goals, composition, organisation of the discussions, and stimuli used in them; *ii*) the technical details of each session, including date, number of participants, language, and format, whether face-to-face or online; and *iii*) the socio-demographic and attitudinal profiles of the participants.

2 DESIGN OF THE FOCUS GROUPS

2.1 Objectives

Focus groups are generally defined as moderated discussions among a small number of participants — typically between six and twelve — centred on a specific topic. Like any research method, they can serve a range of purposes, from observing how group members interact with one another to identifying widely held beliefs and sentiments.¹ They offer the notable advantage of allowing participants to speak in their own words and raise the issues that matter to them, though they are less suited to the analysis of behaviour (as distinct from discourse) or to the exploration of personal and sensitive subjects.

Within the DELIAH project, focus groups serve as a means of investigating socially shared ideas, the variation in those ideas across group members, and the cultural repertoire through which such ideas are expressed, contested, and negotiated. They also provide a space in which to explore participants' experiences of humour in connection to civic and democratic life, and to assess the degree to which these experiences are common to members of different social groups.

More specifically, the focus groups pursue four objectives:

- To examine the extent to which different social groups are exposed to and engage with various forms of socio-political humour;

¹ See, for instance, Smithson, J. (2008). Focus groups. In P. Alasuutari, L. Bickman, J. Brannen (Eds.) *The SAGE Handbook of Social Research Methods* (pp. 357-370). SAGE Publications Ltd, <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781446212165.n21>; and Bloor, M., Frankland, J., Thomas, M., & Robson, K. (2001). *Focus groups in social research*. SAGE Publications Ltd, <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781849209175>.

- To explore the varying degrees to which such groups appreciate different types of socio-political humour and the reasons they give for this, including any connections they draw between engaging with humorous content and their understanding or practice of civic and political participation;
- To investigate attitudes towards the moderation or legal regulation of humorous content; and
- To map the broader repertoire of arguments and frameworks through which humour is understood.

The data generated by the focus groups will be analysed both at the level of individual countries and across the consortium as a whole, and will inform subsequent stages of the DELIAH project. In particular, the findings will contribute to the development of policy recommendations concerning multimedia content moderation and democratic engagement, as well as to further research into the relationship between humour and civic discourse in a European context.

2.2 Composition of the Focus Groups

The focus groups are designed to be relatively homogeneous in composition, so that participants share sufficient common ground to engage in meaningful discussion. In this regard, DELIAH's meta-analysis of the existing literature² identified three key factors. The first is age, and in particular the distinction between younger people, who tend to have greater exposure to and interaction with online humour, and older people. The second is ideology: appreciation of humour is generally shaped by recipients' pre-existing beliefs and attitudes, and given humour's close connection to the negotiation of symbolic boundaries and to contemporary debates about inclusion and exclusion, the GAL/TAN dimension of political competition — that is, the axis running from green, alternative, and libertarian positions to traditional, authoritarian, and nationalist ones — is likely to exert the strongest influence on how different individuals engage with and respond to humorous content. The third factor is an individual's position within the social structure: the meta-analysis found that members of marginalised groups tend to be more sensitive to harmful humour³ than those belonging to dominant groups, and are also more likely to engage in and appreciate self-parody.

At the same time, the meta-analysis revealed significant gaps in the research on how social groups use and react to humour, particularly when those groups are defined by standard socio-demographic variables. The relevance of age, ideology, and social position may not hold equally across all six DELIAH countries, and there is insufficient evidence regarding how these variables interact with one another or how strongly each is associated with distinctive patterns of exposure to, appreciation of, and engagement with humour at the individual level. Nor is there sufficient basis for confidence that all relevant variables have been identified.

² Engelken-Jorge, M., & Moreno, C. (2025). Meta-analysis of contemporary humour practices and democratic attitudes. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16994515>.

³ Harmful humour refers to humour practices that are intended to or which actually contribute to undermining democracy, to promoting an authoritarian regime or actor, to excluding some social groups, or to organising social relations in a non-egalitarian way.

These gaps in the literature have several implications for the sampling of participants. Variation beyond the three variables identified above must be accounted for, including country-specific factors such as differences in the organisation of political competition and social relations. The salience of particular social divisions varies considerably across the consortium: in Belgium, for instance, the distinction between Flanders and Wallonia is of central importance, whereas in Spain and Germany it is the north/south and east/west divides, among others, that are most significant. The composition of the focus groups must therefore strike a balance between sufficient consistency to allow cross-national comparison and testing of the robustness of findings, and sufficient flexibility to accommodate the particularities of each national context.

In light of these considerations, four broadly comparable focus groups have been conducted in each of the DELIAH countries, supplemented by a fifth group per country designed to minimise the underrepresentation of social groups that may be relevant but are not captured by the standard composition. The make-up of this additional group has been determined on a country-by-country basis.

Accordingly, the four standard focus groups are defined as follows:

Focus Group 1 consists predominantly of conservative young men. Participants are aged between 18 and 29, with a gender split of approximately 70% men and 30% women. At least half of the participants should have completed, or be enrolled in, a Level 5 or higher qualification — according to European Qualifications Framework (EQF) — though all participants must meet a minimum threshold of secondary education. This group is intended to represent socially conservative — that is, TAN — perspectives, and is likely to include individuals with significant exposure to and engagement with harmful humour, both online and offline. The minimum education requirement is intended to facilitate discussion, given the well-established association between educational attainment and political interest, knowledge of current affairs, and rhetorical ability.⁴

Focus Group 2 consists predominantly of progressive young women, and may also include non-binary or gender-diverse participants. Participants are aged between 18 and 29, with a gender split of approximately 70% women and 30% men. At least 60% of participants should have completed, or be enrolled in, university-level education. This group is intended to represent socially progressive — that is, GAL — perspectives, and is likely to include individuals who are familiar with harmful humour and critical of it, whether encountered online or offline.

Focus Group 3 comprises participants aged between 40 and 60 who reside in a city in the cultural centre of their country. The group should be evenly split between men and women, and all participants should have completed a Level 6 or higher qualification. Participants should be of middle or upper income. This group is intended to represent the views and experiences of those who are culturally and economically influential, whose tastes and practices are likely either to define or to reflect prevailing societal standards.

Focus Group 4 comprises men, women, and potentially non-binary or gender-diverse participants aged between 20 and 35, all with an immigration background, living in a city, town, or

⁴ Inglehart, R. & Welzel, C. (2005). *Modernization, Cultural Change and Democracy: The Human Development Sequence*. Cambridge University Press. Prior, M. (2019). *Hooked: How Politics Captures People's Interest*. Cambridge University Press.

suburb. The sample should achieve a reasonable gender balance, and at least half of participants should have completed, or be enrolled in, a Level 5 or higher qualification. This group is intended to represent the views and experiences of individuals whose tastes and practices may be at odds with dominant societal norms. As with Focus Group 1, the minimum education threshold is intended to support productive discussion.

Focus Group 5 is tailored to the specific national context of each country, as follows:

Belgium: Participants are men and women aged between 40 and 60, evenly split by gender, with middle or upper incomes and a Level 6 or higher qualification. They should reside in a city considered part of the cultural centre of Flanders. In addition to this fifth group, the remaining Belgian focus groups are assigned specific regional locations: Focus Group 1 is to be conducted in Flanders, Focus Group 2 in Wallonia, Focus Group 3 in a city in the centre of Wallonia, and Focus Group 4 in Brussels and its surrounding suburbs. Taken together, these arrangements are intended to capture some of the regional variation arising from Belgium's linguistically divided public spheres and the crystallisation of political conflict around the country's linguistic cleavage.⁵

Estonia: Participants are men and women aged between 45 and 60, residing in Ida-Virumaa. The group should be balanced by gender, and at least half of participants should have completed secondary or vocational education (EQF Levels 4–5). As this focus group is conducted in Russian, all participants must have an excellent command of that language. Focus Group 5 in Estonia is designed to capture the perspectives of citizens living outside the major urban centres, where levels of social trust, political participation, and access to Estonian-language media and cultural content tend to differ from the national average. This group complements the other Estonian focus groups by incorporating the voices of older, regionally peripheral, and linguistically distinct populations.

Germany: Participants are men and women aged between 40 and 60, evenly split by gender, all residing in East Germany. This group is designed to explore how living in the eastern part of the country shapes attitudes towards humour and patterns of engagement with it.⁶ The age range has been chosen to limit internal heterogeneity and ensure that participants have sufficient common ground for discussion. It also facilitates comparison with Focus Group 3.

Netherlands: Participants are men and women aged between 45 and 60, evenly split by gender, all living in rural areas. This group is designed to explore how the urban/rural divide — which research has shown to be a significant social fault line in the Netherlands⁷ — influences attitudes towards humour and engagement with it. As with the German group, the age range has been set to reduce heterogeneity, support productive discussion, and enable comparison with Focus Group 3.

⁵ Lacey, J. (2017). *Centripetal Democracy: Democratic Legitimacy and Political Identity in Belgium, Switzerland, and the European Union*. Oxford University Press.

⁶ Mau, S. (2024). *Ungleich vereint. Warum der Osten anders bleibt*. Suhrkamp.

⁷ Huijsmans, T., Hartevelde, E., van der Brug, W. & Lancee, B. (2021). Are cities ever more cosmopolitan? Studying trends in urban-rural divergence of cultural attitudes. *Political Geography*, 86: 102353, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polgeo.2021.102353>.

Slovakia: Participants are men and women aged between 45 and 60, evenly split by gender, with non-tertiary educational attainment (EQF Levels 3–5), and all residing in rural areas. This group is designed to examine how the urban/rural divide in Slovakia shapes attitudes towards humour and interaction with humorous content.⁸ The same rationale applies to the age range as in the German and Dutch cases: it limits internal heterogeneity, facilitates discussion, and allows for comparison with Focus Group 3.

Spain: Participants are men and women aged 50 or older, with lower or middle incomes and qualifications at EQF Levels 3–5, living in rural areas, towns, or suburbs in the southern periphery of the country. Focus Group 5 in Spain is designed to address the underrepresentation of certain socio-demographic groups in Focus Groups 1 to 4.

In all cases, each focus group aims to include between seven and nine participants, not counting the moderator, all of whom are expected to have an excellent command of the national language or languages in which the session is conducted. This requirement facilitates discussion, but also has implications for who can be recruited. In addition, at least two participants in each group should be *active users of socio-political humour*,⁹ and at least three should be *politically active*¹⁰ or *civically engaged*.¹¹ These participants are expected to act as catalysts for discussion.

2.3 Organisation of the Discussion

The focus groups are structured around three successive sections, each with a distinct purpose, and move participants progressively from general reflection on humour and public life towards more focused and potentially contentious debates about the regulation of humorous content. To facilitate discussion, various types of stimuli are used, including printed examples of humorous content, satirical videos, and judicial cases involving transgressive humour.

More specifically, the focus groups open with an **introductory section** designed to put participants at ease and establish a conversational tone before the substantive discussion begins. The

⁸ Harmaňoš, T. & Plešivčák, M. (2021). Geography of the conservative-liberal cleavage and selected factors influencing the distribution of conservative and liberal voters in Slovakia. *Geographia Cassoviensis*, 15(2): 186-203, <https://doi.org/10.33542/GC2021-2-05>.

⁹ *Active users of socio-political humour* are focus group participants who specifically pay for humour about political or social topics, or who regularly engage in at least two of the following practices: reading satirical magazines or cartoons about political or social topics; attending or watching stand-up comedy shows about political or social topics; watching satirical news shows or other humorous shows about political or social topics; following online comedians who address political or social topics; visiting websites that include humour about political or social topics; or sharing memes or other humorous content about political or social topics.

¹⁰ *Politically active* participants are defined as those who report an interest in politics or have taken part in any form of non-electoral political participation in the last twelve months.

¹¹ *Civically engaged* participants are defined as those who have participated in any activity of an organisation with volunteering activities, an organisation active in the domain of climate change or environmental issues, an organisation promoting human rights or global development, or a political party or any other political organisation in the last twelve months.

moderator invites each participant to introduce themselves briefly, with a light-hearted ice-breaker prompt serving to lower inhibitions and encourage informal interaction. The group is then gently oriented towards the session's central themes through two opening questions. The first invites participants to situate themselves in relation to public and political life — whether they tend to disengage from such matters, engage with them seriously, or approach them through a humorous lens. The second, broader question asks participants to reflect on what role, if any, they think humour can play in public life. These questions are deliberately brief and open-ended, intended less to generate extended debate than to prime participants and begin surfacing the assumptions and dispositions they bring to the topic.

Section 2 is devoted to socio-political humour itself. Rather than asking participants to discuss the topic in the abstract, the moderator introduces a series of humorous stimuli — memes, cartoons, activist materials, and short videos — to anchor the conversation in concrete examples. Participants are asked to examine the materials individually and complete a short questionnaire before the group discussion begins, ensuring that each person forms their own initial impressions. The subsequent discussion moves from first reactions — whether participants are familiar with the forms of humour presented, whether anything surprised them positively or negatively — to more evaluative questions about personal preferences and the likelihood of sharing particular examples with others.

Once the stimuli have been discussed, the discussion broadens its scope considerably. The moderator reminds participants that socio-political humour extends well beyond the specific examples shown, and that its content can range from the mild to the genuinely provocative. Participants are then invited to reflect on their own everyday habits: what kinds of humorous content they seek out or receive, whether they pay for it, and how and with whom they share it, whether through social media, messaging applications, email, or face-to-face conversation. This portion of the discussion is designed to ground subsequent exchanges in participants' lived experience rather than hypothetical or normative reasoning.

The section concludes with a structured debate about the public role of humour. The moderator presents two contrasting positions: one emphasising humour's potential to harm, polarise, spread misinformation, and trivialise serious issues; the other stressing its capacity to inform, challenge taboos, foster solidarity, and reach audiences that more conventional forms of communication might not. Participants are asked to reflect on these positions in light of the kinds of humour they actually encounter in their daily lives, and to be as specific as possible in their responses. The section also invites participants to identify any recent trends in the public use of humour, such as shifts in tone, target, or medium, and to consider what role, if any, social media platforms have played in driving such changes.

Section 3 turns to the question of how — and indeed whether — socio-political humour should be regulated or moderated. Here the moderator introduces a further set of stimuli, this time in the form of real judicial cases involving humorous expression and freedom of speech. Participants are invited to deliberate as a form of popular jury, considering the arguments that might be made by both the defence and the prosecution before arriving at their own view of what a reasonable verdict would look like and how the situation might have been handled outside the courts. The moderator then reveals the actual outcomes of the cases, prompting a further round of discussion about whether participants consider the verdicts fair and what, if anything, ought to change in how such cases are approached. The section closes with a sequence of broader

normative questions that build naturally on the preceding deliberation: whether humour should be subject to any form of control at all; what mechanisms — judicial, regulatory, or informal social sanction — participants would consider appropriate; and whether effective and desirable regulation is best pursued at a national, European, or global level.

2.4 Stimuli

The focus groups make use of eight humorous stimuli and two judicial cases, presented to participants across three A3 sheets. The first sheet contains stimuli 1 to 6, each accompanied by a short questionnaire in which participants are asked to indicate their level of agreement with four statements — ‘I think it’s funny’, ‘I like its aesthetics’, ‘I think it’s creative’, and ‘I agree with the message’ — using an emoji-based scale running from complete disagreement to complete agreement. This individual rating exercise serves a dual purpose: it gives participants time to reflect on the different dimensions of each example before the group discussion begins, and it generates quantitative data on humour appreciation that complements the qualitative material produced by the discussion itself. The second sheet follows the same format but refers to stimuli 7 and 8, which take the form of videos and are therefore presented separately. The third sheet presents two real judicial cases involving humorous expression, providing participants with the relevant background information but withholding the actual verdicts until after the group has deliberated.

Stimuli 1 to 6 and the two judicial cases are common to all six countries and have been translated into the relevant focus group languages; stimuli 7 and 8, by contrast, are country-specific. Licences have been obtained for the use of all materials within the focus group setting, though these do not in all cases extend to publication, and links are therefore provided in this document rather than the images or videos themselves. The selection of stimuli illustrates a range of humour genres and content — including memes, cartoons, culture jamming, and satirical video — but is not intended to be exhaustive. Because the materials are shared across groups and have been chosen with ethical considerations in mind, some participants may find certain examples less provocative or engaging than they might wish; this is an acknowledged methodological limitation, but one that cannot be avoided without risking exposure to content that could cause distress.

Stimuli 1 and 2 are memes — a format widely associated with the expression of political views in accessible and often humorous terms, particularly among younger audiences. Memes can carry messages ranging from the innocuous to the deeply divisive, and their online circulation has frequently been linked to political polarisation and hate speech. The examples chosen stop well short of hate speech, but both carry clear socio-political intent and employ familiar meme templates, illustrating the genre’s characteristic logic of endlessly recombining existing cultural material to produce new meanings. [Stimulus 2](#) alludes to the rhetoric of the MAGA movement, gesturing towards the transnationalisation of political discourse, while [Stimulus 1](#)¹² engages with questions of gender but does so ambiguously: although it can be read as gently mocking men,

¹² Stimulus 1 reads: What are we? / Men! / What do we want? / We want our girlfriends to stop giving us orders! / And when do we want it? / What time, darling? At eight o’clock. / At eight o’clock!

it simultaneously draws on and reinforces the stereotype of women as natural managers of the domestic sphere.

Stimuli 3 and 4 are cartoons with somewhat less transparent socio-political meanings. [Stimulus 3](#) touches on gender and sexual diversity but resists a single interpretation: it could be read as an affirmation of identity politics or equally as a satirical comment on how far such politics has been taken. [Stimulus 4](#) is a variation on the long-established tradition of the moron joke — a form of humour historically directed at rural communities, regional groups, or particular ethnic or national groups, and widely regarded as a vehicle for reproducing social stereotypes and symbolically marginalising certain groups. At the same time, its inclusion raises questions about whether contemporary sensitivities risk over-interpreting what has long been treated as a largely innocuous genre.

[Stimulus 5](#) is an example of culture jamming — a form of activist practice that subverts mainstream media and commercial imagery, typically through humour. Its inclusion invites participants to reflect on the appropriateness and effectiveness of humour as a tool of social protest. [Stimulus 6](#) is a cartoon sketch exemplifying the familiar use of humour to critique political and economic elites. It carries additional significance in light of its origins: it was created by Ann Telnaes, a former cartoonist for The Washington Post, and targeted a group of prominent billionaires who had sought to cultivate favour with Donald Trump. The cartoon was rejected by the newspaper; Telnaes maintained that the decision was politically motivated and resigned in protest, while the paper attributed it to editorial duplication. The case thus illustrates both the practice of using humour to hold elites to account and the ways in which such humour can itself be subject to censorship.

Stimuli 7 and 8 are video-based and country-specific. For [Belgium](#), [Germany](#), [the Netherlands](#), [Slovakia](#), and [Spain](#), Stimulus 7 is drawn from the widely circulated 'America First, [Country] Second' series, which originated with a sketch by the Dutch comedian Arjen Lubach and was subsequently replicated across numerous countries. Each video takes the form of a mock official address to President Trump, parodying both his rhetoric and the distinctive features of the country in question. The Belgian, German, and Dutch versions are shown in full; the Slovak and Spanish versions have been edited for length. [Estonia](#), for which no equivalent video exists, is instead shown a 2015 parody by the comedy group Tujurikkuja, which, while it does not engage with Trump, operates in a similar spirit of national self-parody. Only the first three minutes are screened. Stimulus 8 consists of excerpts from national satirical television programmes addressing climate change or related themes such as renewable energy. These videos target a range of positions — including both climate change denial and climate activism — and are presented in each country's official national language.¹³ The video shown to the Estonian focus group in Ida-Virumaa is accordingly in Estonian rather than Russian.

¹³ More specifically, these are the videos for [Estonia](#), [Belgium-Flanders](#), [Belgium-Wallonia](#) (up to 02:29), [Germany](#), [the Netherlands](#) (00:03 – 03:30), [Slovakia](#) (up to 02:57), and [Spain](#) (00:38 – 3:12).

The two judicial cases used in the final section of each focus group are *Ward v. Quebec* (2021) and *Z.B. v. France* (2021).¹⁴ These cases were selected because they represent opposing positions on the limits of humorous expression: one upholds a broad interpretation of freedom of speech, while the other supports restrictions on humorous communication. Both cases are used across all thirty focus groups.

3 IMPLEMENTATION OF THE FOCUS GROUPS

The focus groups were conducted between 2nd and 12th March 2026 by Ipsos, the international market and public opinion research company that won the 33/25 bidding process initiated by the University of the Basque Country. Ipsos was also responsible for recruiting the participants, which took place during the second half of February 2026. Shortly after the focus groups were implemented, the videos and audio recordings, the sheets used to present the humorous stimuli and collect participants' assessments of the humorous examples, and the discussion transcripts in both the original languages and English were delivered to DELIAH researchers. The DELIAH team also had the opportunity to attend the focus groups in person or online, which they did on ten occasions. Additionally, Ipsos reported to the DELIAH researchers after the first focus group in each country to confirm that the discussion guide and the stimuli were working as expected.

The focus groups ran according to plan. Only two incidents are worth mentioning. Due to a last-minute cancellation, only six participants took part in Focus Group 4 in Germany, which falls below the threshold of seven participants established for the focus groups. Additionally, the local Ipsos team in Slovakia misunderstood the recruitment guidelines for Focus Group 1, which resulted in this focus group comprising three conservative participants and four progressive ones. Although this represents a significant deviation, the data has been retained, as this affects only one focus group. The data will be used to study the influence of a mixed ideological composition on group dynamics among young people and, in particular, on the repertoire of frames and arguments they employ to make sense of socio-political humour.

Table 1: Focus Groups in Belgium

	Number of participants	Date & Time	Location	Type	Language
Focus Group 1	9	2 March, 18:30	Antwerp	face-to-face	Dutch
Focus Group 2	8	5 March, 18:30	Charleroi	face-to-face	French
Focus Group 3	9	10 March, 18:30	Liège	face-to-face	French

¹⁴ Godioli, A. & Young, J. (2023). Humor and Free Speech: A Comparative Analysis of Global Case Law. *Columbia Global Freedom of Expression*, Special Collection. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8105760>; and *Columbia Global Freedom of Expression Database*, cases [39041](#) and [46883/15](#).

Focus Group 4	9	4 March, 18:30	Brussels	face-to-face	French
Focus Group 5	9	12 March, 18:30	Ghent	face-to-face	Dutch

Table 2: Focus Groups in Estonia

	Number of participants	Date & Time	Location	Type	Language
Focus Group 1	8	8 March, 17:00	Tallin	face-to-face	Estonian
Focus Group 2	8	8 March, 14:00	Tallin	face-to-face	Estonian
Focus Group 3	9	3 March, 18:00	Tartu	face-to-face	Estonian
Focus Group 4	8	12 March, 18:00	Tallin	face-to-face	Estonian
Focus Group 5	8	11 March, 18:00	Ida-Virumaa	online	Russian

Table 3: Focus Groups in Germany

	Number of participants	Date & Time	Location	Type	Language
Focus Group 1	7	10 March, 18:30	Munich	online	German
Focus Group 2	8	11 March, 17:30	Hamburg	face-to-face	German
Focus Group 3	8	11 March, 20:00	Hamburg	face-to-face	German
Focus Group 4	6	12 March, 20:00	Hamburg	face-to-face	German
Focus Group 5	8	12 March, 17:30	Saxony	online	German

Table 4: Focus Groups in the Netherlands

	Number of participants	Date & Time	Location	Type	Language
Focus Group 1	8	4 March, 19:00	Brabant/ Limburg	online	Dutch
Focus Group 2	8	3 March, 19:00	Amsterdam	face-to-face	Dutch
Focus Group 3	8	3 March, 16:30	Amsterdam	face-to-face	Dutch
Focus Group 4	8	4 March, 16:30	Amsterdam	face-to-face	Dutch
Focus Group 5	8	5 March, 19:00	North Holland	online	Dutch

Table 5: Focus Groups in Slovakia

	Number of participants	Date & time	Location	Type	Language
Focus Group 1	7	5 March, 16:00	Košice	face-to-face	Slovak
Focus Group 2	7	2 March, 15:00	Bratislava	face-to-face	Slovak
Focus Group 3	7	3 March, 15:00	Bratislava	face-to-face	Slovak
Focus Group 4	7	3 March, 17:30	Bratislava	face-to-face	Slovak
Focus Group 5	7	4 March, 15:30	Zvolen	face-to-face	Slovak

Table 6: Focus Groups in Spain

	Number of participants	Date & Time	Location	Type	Language
Focus Group 1	9	2 March, 18:00	Madrid	face-to-face	Spanish
Focus Group 2	8	4 March, 16:00	Barcelona	face-to-face	Spanish
Focus Group 3	9	3 March, 18:00	Madrid	face-to-face	Spanish
Focus Group 4	7	4 March, 18:30	Barcelona	face-to-face	Spanish
Focus Group 5	9	5 March, 16:30	Dos Hermanas	face-to-face	Spanish

4 PROFILES OF THE FOCUS GROUP PARTICIPANTS

The focus groups involved 239 citizens in total. Specifically, 44 individuals participated in Belgium; 41 in Estonia; 37 in Germany; 40 in the Netherlands; 35 in Slovakia; and 42 in Spain, yielding average participation rates of 8.8 participants per group in Belgium; 8.2 in Estonia; 7.4 in Germany; 8.0 in the Netherlands; 7.0 in Slovakia; and 8.4 in Spain — 8.0 across all focus groups combined.

Data about the participants was collected during the recruitment process. This includes information on their age, gender, place of residence, level of education, household income, immigration background, ideological self-placement, civic and political engagement, interest in politics, social trust, satisfaction with democracy, internal political efficacy, and engagement with socio-political humour. While the focus groups were not designed to be statistically representative of the population of each DELIAH country, as discussed in Section 2.2, exploring the participants' profiles is nonetheless relevant. In the remainder of the section information on each of the aforementioned variables is provided, which is used later to identify the profiles of focus group participants.

By gender, the overall sample is balanced: 119 participants self-identified as women and 120 as men. No participant self-identified as non-binary or chose to define themselves according to any other category. By country, most samples are similarly balanced by gender (Figure 1), with the exception of Belgium, where men are slightly overrepresented (24 men vs. 20 women).

Figure 1: Focus group composition by country and gender (number of participants)

Regarding education level, most participants held a university degree or were enrolled in higher education at the time the focus groups were conducted: 44% at undergraduate level and slightly under 21% at master’s level. The picture varies, however, when samples are analysed by country (Figure 2). In Spain and Slovakia in particular, the proportion of participants with non-university education is highest, with just over 50% of participants falling into this group. This is largely attributable to the relationship between national qualification frameworks and the EQF, as well as to how the focus groups in these two countries were defined.

Figure 2: Focus group composition by country and formal level of education (%)

The distribution of participants by age broadly followed a U-shaped curve, with overrepresentation of those aged 20–30 or, in some countries, 20–35, as well as those aged over 40 (Figure 3). In all countries except Estonia, the largest age group is either 21–25 (in Belgium, where it accounts for 30% of participants; the Netherlands, 28%; Slovakia, 23%; and Spain, 26%) or 26–30

(Germany, 30%). In Estonia, the largest age group is 51–55 (24% of participants in that country), closely followed by 26–30 (22%). The average age ranges from 34 to 37 across all countries.

Figure 3: Focus group composition by country and age (%)

Approximately a third of participants reported some form of immigration background, meaning that they were born in a country other than the one in which the focus group took place or, more frequently, that at least one of their parents was born in a different country (Figure 4). In Slovakia and Spain this group is considerably smaller — representing 20% and 26% of participants respectively — in contrast to the remaining DELIAH countries, where an average of 36% of participants in Belgium, Estonia, Germany, and the Netherlands reported an immigration background.

Figure 4: Focus group composition by country and migration background (%)

Regarding participants' income levels, most belong, unsurprisingly, to the middle-income group. However, there is a sizeable representation of lower-income citizens in the Netherlands (23%) and Spain (17%), and of higher-income citizens in Estonia (almost 20%) and Slovakia (17%). In the remaining cases, the number of participants from higher- and lower-income groups is very small (i.e., fewer than five participants) or non-existent.

As regards participants' reported ideological beliefs, the sample overrepresents those with GAL positions: 57% vs. 43% (excluding missing cases). In any case, a distinction should be drawn between Belgium, Germany, the Netherlands, and Spain on the one hand, and Estonia and Slovakia on the other, as different methods were used to measure citizens' ideological positions in these two sets of countries. In the former group, participants' self-placement on the left-right continuum was used as a proxy indicator of their GAL-TAN positions.¹⁵ The sample is evenly split between those with GAL and TAN positions in Spain, whilst in the Netherlands and, particularly, in Belgium, citizens holding TAN beliefs are overrepresented (Figure 5). Participants with GAL beliefs are, in turn, overrepresented in Germany. A closer look at participants' self-placement on the ideological continuum reveals that positions range from 1 (one participant in Germany) to 9 (two participants in the Netherlands). However, almost 90% report relatively moderate positions, i.e., between 3 (centre-left) and 7 (centre-right).

¹⁵ Steiner, N. D. (2023). The shifting issue content of left-right identification: cohort differences in Western Europe. *West European Politics*, 47(6): 1276–1303. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01402382.2023.2214875>.

Figure 5: Focus group composition in Belgium, Germany, the Netherlands, and Spain by ideology (%)

In Estonia and Slovakia, in contrast, five items were used to measure participants’ ideological position on the GAL–TAN dimension.¹⁶ Given how this concept was operationalised, no ‘centre’ position was available, resulting in all participants being categorised as either GAL or TAN.¹⁷ In both countries, the sample is skewed towards the GAL end, with only around a third of participants expressing TAN beliefs in Estonia—a share similar to that of Belgium and only slightly lower than that of the Netherlands—and 14% (i.e., five participants) in Slovakia (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Focus group composition in Estonia and Slovakia by ideology (%)

Concerning other attitudinal variables, the sample is relatively evenly split between civically engaged participants (46%) and those who do not qualify as civically engaged (54%) according to the types of organisations they belong to. In Spain (67%) and Germany (54%), the proportion

¹⁶ These include questions about EU integration (whether it has gone too far or should go further), the effect of immigration on the labour market (whether immigrants take jobs away from nationals or not), public security (whether immigrants make crime problems worse or not), gender equality (whether men have more right to a job than women when jobs are scarce), and sexual diversity (whether gays and lesbians should be free to live their lives as they wish).

¹⁷ For details, see Moreno, C. et al. (2025). D3 / D2.1 – Common Framework for the Focus Groups. *Deliverable of the DELIAH project*. <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e52460f898&ap- pld=PPGMS>.

of civically engaged participants is clearly above the average (Figure 7), whilst the opposite holds for the Netherlands and Slovakia, which have the highest proportions of civically disengaged participants (68% and 66%, respectively).

Figure 7: Focus group composition by country and civic engagement (%)

Furthermore, the overwhelming majority of participants — 85% — qualify as ‘active users of humour’. This is especially the case in Spain and the Netherlands, where 95% and 93% of focus group participants respectively can be considered active humour users. In Estonia and Belgium, the proportion of non-active humour users is notably higher (27% and 23% respectively).

In terms of internal political efficacy, most participants report feeling ‘a little’ (31%) or ‘somewhat confident’ (48%) in their ability to participate in politics. In Germany, however, an unusually large proportion (43%) report being ‘very confident’, whilst in Slovakia those reporting being ‘not at all confident’ (26%) or ‘a little confident’ (34%) are in the majority.

Regarding satisfaction with democracy, the sample is relatively evenly split, with satisfaction prevailing in Belgium and, in particular, in Estonia and the Netherlands. By contrast, dissatisfaction prevails in Germany, Spain, and especially Slovakia. Most participants, however, express moderate degrees of satisfaction or dissatisfaction (i.e., ‘somewhat satisfied’ or ‘somewhat dissatisfied’).

Finally, a slightly larger proportion of participants express feelings of distrust (55%) than social trust (41%). This is particularly the case in Estonia (59%), Belgium (66%), and above all Slovakia (94%), where distrustful participants predominate. By contrast, in Spain (52%), Germany (57%), and the Netherlands (63%), participants expressing social trust are in the majority.

In order to identify recurring combinations of characteristics across participants, a K-modes cluster analysis has been implemented, retaining 202 of the 239 participants.¹⁸ It yields a four-cluster solution (Figure 8).¹⁹ The resulting clusters should not be understood as rigid, mutually

¹⁸ The 37 excluded cases have missing values on ideological self-placement, social trust, political efficacy, or satisfaction with democracy, which are the most analytically sensitive variables.

¹⁹ K=4 was retained on the grounds that it offered the most interpretable set of profiles.

exclusive types into which every individual neatly falls, but rather as a useful simplification of the dataset. Each profile can be thought of as a ‘typical’ combination of characteristics that a substantial share of participants approximates, even if no single individual matches it exactly on every dimension. The four profiles are as follows:

Profile 1: Civically disengaged and socially distrustful conservative men who are satisfied with democracy (n=71, 35%). This is the largest cluster. Mostly young (59%) and overwhelmingly male (83%), urban-dwelling, with tertiary education (EQF6, 61%), no immigration background, and a TAN ideological orientation (82%). This group is satisfied with democracy (66%), but largely not civically engaged (65%) and socially distrustful (65%). Political efficacy is moderate.

Profile 2: Progressive, trustful, and civically engaged young women with an immigration background (n=43, 21%). This is a socially trusting (81%) and civically active (77%) group. Predominantly female (74%) and young (70%), with a strikingly high proportion reporting an immigration background (72%) — the only cluster where this is a majority characteristic. GAL-oriented (77%), they are satisfied with democracy (70%) and confident in their political efficacy.

Profile 3: Progressive, highly educated, middle-aged women, dissatisfied with democracy (n=40, 20%). Defined by the combination of high education (EQF 7 in 44% of cases — the highest of any cluster), older age (88% over-40), GAL orientation (85%), dissatisfaction with democracy (70%), and lower levels of internal political efficacy (50% feel ‘a little confident’). Civic engagement is, however, relatively high (70%), but social trust is lower than in the previous group, with 60% reporting that they are trusting, while 40% are not.

Profile 4: Progressive, civically disengaged, and distrustful young people with secondary education, who are dissatisfied with democracy (n=48, 24%). The most attitudinally pessimistic cluster. Young (77%) and majority female (58%), but with a sizeable presence of men (42%), this group reports the lowest education levels across the sample (63% at EQF 4). Ideologically GAL (75%), they are almost uniformly distrustful (94%), dissatisfied with democracy (73%), and disengaged from civic life (83%).

Figure 8: Profiles from the K-modes cluster analysis

The distribution of these profiles by country reveals some striking patterns (Figure 9). Belgium stands out as the country most dominated by Profile 1, which accounts for over half of its (clustered) participants (53%). This is consistent with the higher-than-average share of TAN-oriented citizens noted in the descriptive analysis. Profiles 3 and 4 each account for roughly 18% of the remainder, Profile 2 for 12%, i.e., 4 participants.

In Slovakia, Profile 4 is by far the dominant type (51%), while Profile 2 is almost entirely absent. This maps closely onto Slovakia’s distinctive attitudinal fingerprint in the descriptive data — near-universal distrust, low political efficacy, and high dissatisfaction with democracy. Profile 3 also has its highest country-level share here (29%), reflecting the concentration of older, educated, GAL-leaning and dissatisfied participants.

Germany is the most evenly distributed country, with all four profiles each capturing between 21% and 29% of the sample. (Germany, however, is the country with the highest number of missing cases, thus its within-country percentages should be interpreted with some caution.) The picture is similar in Estonia, although somewhat less balanced, with Profiles 2, 3, and 4 each at around 20% and Profile 1 at 38%.

The Netherlands and Spain share a similar shape: Profiles 1 and 2 together account for roughly three quarters of each country’s participants. The Netherlands in particular has almost no representative of Profile 3 (n=3), which aligns with its above-average satisfaction with democracy in the full-sample analysis.

Figure 9: Distribution of K=4 profiles across countries

